

Original Research

Nociception for monitoring preemptive analgesia before an endotracheal suctioning: a randomised trial.

Abstract

Background: Pain during aspiration is frequent in critically ill patients. Standardized protocols are needed to manage the preemptive analgesia before interventions.

Methods: A multicentre randomized clinical trial was conducted to compare the percentage of patients with pain between the experimental and control groups according to Behavioural Pain Scale (BPS), Scale of Behavior Indicators of Pain (ESCID), and pupillary dilation reflex (PDR). Patients older than 18 years, under analgo-sedation, with BPS=3, ESCID=0, and RASS -1 and -4 were studied. We randomly two treatment groups. Control group: preemptive analgesia (PreA) before endotracheal suctioning (ETA) was administered according to the clinical criteria. In the experimental group, PreA was administered in patients with a PDR $\geq 11.5\%$ after a stimulus of 20mA. The PreA regardless of the group to which the patients belonged, was fentanyl one $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ iv bolus. The primary outcome was pain after ETA. A multivariate logistic regression study was performed. $p < 0.05$

Results: Ninety-two patients were measured, with 51 in control and 41 in intervention groups. The patients with pain by BPS was 58.8% and 46.3%, respectively; 64.6% and 48.6% by ESCID, and 58.8% and 39.0% by PDR. Lower pain risk observed in experimental group (BPS: OR= 0.34, 95% CI: 0.12-0.99, $p = 0.048$; ESCID: OR= 0.29, 95% CI: 0.09-0.88, $p = 0.030$; PDR: OR= 0.27, 95% CI: 0.08-0.86, $p = 0.027$).

Conclusions: The PreA monitorization before ETA, guided by pupillometry, has a protective effect on the development of pain. This protection is irrespective of the sex, severity level, BIS, remifentanyl and PreA.

Key words: analgesia; critical care; nociception; pain measurement; Reflex, Pupillary

Introduction

The management and prevention of pain in patients who are unable to communicate, especially those who are limited in their behavioural response, remains a challenge.

Patients receive a baseline analgesia regimen following clinical guidelines and in-hospital protocols that attempt to provide an optimal level of comfort during ICU admission. Despite this, their pain intensity increases significantly during standard care procedures (Aslan et al., 2024; López de Audícana-Jimenez de Aberasturi et al., 2023a; Robleda et al., 2016).

The discomfort generated during procedures often leads to mechanical ventilation mismatches, hemodynamic instability, and increased intracranial pressure, directly affecting the patient's condition. It is essential to accurately assess and treat pain in hemodynamically unstable critically ill patients. However, the percentage of patients receiving preemptive analgesia (PreA) before intervention is less than 10% (López López et al., 2013).

Pain associated with interventions in critically ill patients has been analyzed, but there is still insufficient evidence on the management of PreA before interventions in sedated patients. Currently, the assignment of PreA before care is based on clinical criteria with the risk of making inappropriate adjustments to their analgesia needs.

New tools for indirect pain measurement and balance between analgesia and nociception in surgical patients have been studied (Guglielminotti et al., 2015). PDR corresponds to an autonomic reflex reaction of pupillary dilation to noxious stimuli, with a direct physiological correlation to pain perception and nociception. Pupillometry would be one approach to studying the nociceptive response in sedated critically ill patients by examining the pupillary reactivity reflex. The pupillary pain index (PPI), based on the analysis of the variation of the PDR secondary to a consecutive gradual nociceptive stimulation of up to 60 mA, is a tool for monitoring analgesia in the anaesthetized patient (Bartholmes et al., 2020). A work studied patients with RASS -5, and encouraging results were observed in the critical patient setting (Vinclair et al., 2019). Still, the intensity of these stimuli would not be well tolerated in patients with a more superficial level of sedation, as in patients in critical care units (Paulus et al., 2013; Sabourdin et al., 2018). Recently, a study conducted on patients with RASS scores between -4 and -1 found that a 20 mA

stimulus was the best way to detect nociception in this patient group, with optimal diagnostic performance values (López de Audicana-Jimenez de Aberasturi et al., 2023b).

This study compares the pain after ETA by BPS and ESCID pain scales and PDR in mechanically ventilated patients administered pupillometry-guided PreA versus standard clinical practice (SCP) before endotracheal suctioning. The clinical performance of the 20 mA stimulus to detect the need for PreA before potentially painful interventions is unknown. Analysis of the patient's nociceptive response to low-intensity stimuli could be a tool to individually and objectively monitor the PreA before daily critical care interventions.

Methods

Design

A multicenter randomized clinical trial was conducted between 1/11/2019 and 21/01/2023. We compared the presence of pain according to PDR, BPS, and ESCID in patients monitored with pupillometry vs. SCP.

Participants

The study enrolled patients under 18 undergoing mechanical ventilation for pain relief. Participants had a baseline ESCID score of 0, a baseline BPS score of 3, and a RASS score ranging from -1 to -4. They were hemodynamically stable. Patients with ophthalmologic pathology with pupillary involvement, involvement of the III cranial nerve, Glasgow coma scale < 6, intracranial hypertension, and under treatment with drugs such as atropine, clonidine, dexmedetomidine, tramadol, ketamine, adrenaline, calcium antagonists and antiemetics were excluded.

Patients who showed hemodynamic and respiratory instability during protocol application were withdrawn from the study.

Baseline clinical data, including age, sex, hospital admission reason, APACHE II, Glasgow Coma Scale, and basal sedative and analgesic drug and dose, were recorded from the patient's digital medical history

before the intervention. Measurements were taken during the first week of ICU stay, starting on the second day of admission.

All patients' relatives and legal representatives consented to the patient's participation in the study.

Study protocol

Patients were sedated and anaesthetized according to the current sedation protocol (Hariharan et al.,2017) and not administered any sedative or analgesic drugs in addition to continuous infusions of sedative or analgesic medications once the protocol started. In addition, a comprehensive safety protocol for tracheal suctioning and the use of opioids and sedatives was developed and implemented.

Patients in the experimental group underwent a pupillometry-monitored analgesia. A calibrated 20mA stimulus was given before ETA, and the PDR was analyzed. In patients with a PDR of 11.5% or more, PreA was administered before ETA. In those patients who did not register PDR greater than 11.5% by pupillometry, ETA was performed continuously without PreA to that already available. Patients in the control group were administered PreA before ETA, according to the unit's SCP and recommendations for pain management in critically ill patients (Barr. et al., 2013; Devlin et al.,2018). The healthcare team responsible for the patient made clinical decisions regarding this treatment (Fig. 1).

Patients were randomly assigned to each group guided by a digital randomization application of the hospital's research unit. The randomization process was not disclosed to the clinicians or other healthcare staff involved in the study. The randomization sequence followed a 1:1 scheme. After all patients' relatives and legal representatives consented to the patient's participation in the study, the patient's demographic data were completed in the data collection booklet.

All patients in whom PreA was required, regardless of the group to which the patients belonged, received fentanyl one $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ iv bolus.

After endotracheal aspiration, pain was assessed by pupillometry and with the BPS and ESCID scales in all patients in both groups. Three independent investigators' measurements were blinded to each other's performed pain assessment. A nurse who was not part of the study conducted endotracheal aspiration.

Outcomes measurements

Pupillary measurements were performed with the Neurolight AlgiScan® portable video pupillometer (ID Company, Marseille, France). The pupillometer recorded an optimal impedance level before the stimulations, guaranteeing the quality of the measurements and following the protocol recommended by the manufacturer. The patients were required to remain in a supine position. Measurements were performed with the pupillometer's silicone enveloping shield over the eye under study, avoiding direct light sources on the patient. We used a small Steri-Strip® to hide the contralateral eye of the study. Before measuring pupillary variation, we turned off the lights and silenced the alarms. The stimulus was performed after 2-3 seconds of stabilization of the pupil size to the dark environment generated by the eye shield. In patients in the intervention group, a calibrated electrical stimulus of 20 mA was applied through an electrode placed on the ulnar nerve of the hand with the pupillometer in TETANOS mode. The PDR value was analysed, and PreA was administered if appropriate.

The variable "PreA" was used to record the administration of fentanyl before ETA, with responses being either "yes" or "no."

The presence of pain after ETA was measured using the BPS, ESCID scales, and PDR. The BPS and ESCID were scales for measuring behavioural responses to painful stimuli. BPS has a maximum score of 12 and a minimum of 3 points. The ESCID is a modified version of the CAMPBELL scale. It has five behavioural items (facial musculature, calmness, muscle tone, verbal response, and comfort), with a total score range from 0 to 10 and allows the graduation of pain in 0: no pain; from 1 to 3 mild pain; from 4 to 6: moderate pain; from 7 to 10 severe pain. We utilized the pupillometer in "DRP" mode to measure pain presence via PDR in patients from both groups during ATE. PDR was measured for 20 seconds.

Scores on the behavioural pain scale (BPS and ESCID) (Ahlers et al., 2010; Latorre et al., 2016) with an increase of 1 point or more over the values of 3 and 0 points were considered indicative of pain.

Regarding the pupillary dilation reflex to nociceptive stimulation, PDR values above 11.5% indicated the presence of pain (López de Audicana-Jimenez de Aberasturi et al., 2023a).

An external technician from the Basque Research Institute BIOEF monitored the study. He was responsible for verifying that the data entered in the data collection notebook corresponded appropriately to those in the clinical records. He supervised the centres through on-site visits, protocol verification, and

the optimal completion of databases. All data were collected in a private repository of the XXXX health system XXXXXX.

Statistical analysis

To detect a proportion of subjects with pain according to the BPS / ESCID scale of 31% in control group and 69% in experimental group, with a power of 90%, it was necessary to study 82 patients. Considering a 10% loss rate, 92 patients were included. The randomized clinical trial was analyzed using intention-to-treat.

We described the characteristics of the sample. Quantitative variables were expressed through central distribution indicators and qualitative variables were expressed as percentages.

The patients with pain according to BPS, ESCID scale, and PDR and PreA were compared between the experimental group (PreA before intervention monitoring according to pupillometry) and control (PreA before intervention monitoring according to SCP) using the Chi-square statistic.

A bivariate analysis was performed to study the association of the factors related to pain with the presence or absence of pain. A multivariate logistic regression study was performed. The group of patients was considered the independent variable, and pain according to PDR, BPS, and ESCID scales was the dependent variable. We adjusted the outcomes for sex, BIS, RASS, APACHE II, remifentanyl, that were considered clinically relevant in the management of pain in the critically ill patient. We adjusted the outcomes also for PreA. The calibration of the three adjusted models was assessed using the Hosmer-Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test.

We used the statistical programs IBM SPSS Statistic version 29.0 and R-studio version 4.1.2 and established an alpha value of 0.05 and a statistical power of 80 %.

Ethics approval

The Clinical Research Ethics Committee of XXX approved the project (CEIC-E; internal code: PI2017100). Under XXX legislation (Royal Decree 223/2004), the study was covered by Professional Civil Liability insurance in any adverse events. Patients' legal representatives were informed and asked for written consent as a requirement for including patients in the study.

Results

A multicenter randomized clinical trial was conducted from November 1, 2019, to January 21, 2023, with 92 patients in total —51 in the control group and 41 in the intervention group. Eleven patients were excluded from the analysis: 7 didn't meet inclusion criteria, two didn't provide consent, and two were withdrawn due to an administrative error (Fig. 2).

The general characteristics of the sample are in Table 1. The groups were homogeneous. All patients had analgo-sedation perfusion with mean BIS of 57.6 ± 17.2 and 63.2 ± 11.9 and a RASS of -3.13 ± 1.07 and -2.91 ± 0.91 respectively. No adverse effects were recorded during the protocol.

Primary outcome

The percentage of patients who experienced pain after ATE was lower among patients belonging to the experimental group according to BPS (46.3% vs. 58.8%), ESCID (41.5% vs. 60.8%), and PDR (39.0% vs. 58.8%) compared to patients in the control group. PDR was the tool that recorded more differences, but we did not find any significant differences between the groups regarding the presence or absence of pain.

Secondary outcomes

In the experimental group, PreA before ETA was prescribed to 43.9% ($p=0.03$) of patients. Meanwhile, in SCP group, PreA was prescribed to 19.6% of patients (Table 2).

The univariate analysis was used to classify pain or absence of pain in patients according to BPS, ESCID, and PDR. The results showed no statistically significant differences between the two groups. For BPS, 38.8% were in the experimental group [OR= 0.61 (95% CI, 0.26 -1.39) ($p=0.234$)]. For ESCID, 35.4% belonged to the experimental group [OR= 0.52 (95% CI, 0.21-1.26) ($p=0.147$)]. Similarly, no statistically significant differences were found in PDR, measured by pupillometry. According to the presence of pain in PDR, 34.8% belong to the experimental group [OR= 0.45 (95% CI, 0.19-1.04) ($p=0.061$)]. The analgesia administered in the groups classified according to pain showed no significant differences classified according to BPS, ESCID, and pupillometry (Table ...)

A multivariate analysis was adjusted for sex, APACHE II ≥ 20 , BIS ≥ 60 , and remifentanyl treatment and PreA were done. We observed significant differences between groups, with a protective effect on pain for the experimental group monitored with pupillometry measured by BPS [OR= 0.34 (95% CI: 0.12- 0.99) (p= 0.048)], ESCID [OR= 0.29 (95% CI: 0.09-0.88) (p= 0.030)] and PDR [OR= 0.27, 95% IC (0.08-0.86) (p= 0.027)]. Hosmer-Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test shows a good calibration for the three adjusted models (Table 3).

Discussion

One of the most important roles of a nurse responsible for a critically ill patient is to provide optimal comfort. A patient's comfort depends on the clinical situation and individual pain tolerance, and overtreatment or undertreatment of pain are conditions that are not free of side effects on the patient. Inadequate pain management could lead to respiratory instability with maladaptation to ventilatory support and cardiovascular instability, with hypotension and hypertension and consequent changes in cerebral blood flow, increased intracranial pressure or myocardial ischemia in patients (Alnajjar et al., 2021). On the other hand, the abuse of opioids has also been associated with side effects such as abdominal ileus, prolongation of mechanical ventilation times, and acquired weakness of the critically ill patient (Moran et al., 2022).

Clinical practice guidelines emphasize pre-procedural pain assessment and PreA before potentially painful stimuli (Devlin et al., 2018). However, in routine clinical SCP, there is a risk of underestimating pain intensity and subsequently undertreating it. Pain associated with procedures was often considered too short-lived to benefit from PreA. Practitioners tend to give more importance to pain management in patients with clinical situations or interventions associated with a subjective perception of pain risk. Pain assessment tends to be less of a priority in sedated patients, resulting in infrequent pain assessments during procedures (Alnajjar et al., 2021). Conversely, although it is not usual, excessive sensitization to pain, i.e., administering analgesics when they are not necessary, would increase their deleterious effects in critically ill patients.

ICU patients often receive baseline analgesia to prevent pain; however, it may not be sufficient during routine care, such as ETA. Behavioural scales allow the detection of changes secondary to potentially

painful procedures but do not predict the possible presence of pain before interventions. The need for premedication before a painful intervention remains unresolved.

A reliable diagnostic tool is essential to determine individual sensitivity to stimuli and the appropriate analgesic dose needed to ensure adequate individualised pain management in critically ill patients. At present, the nurse makes PreA decisions subjectively based on her experience and clinical knowledge (Taínta et al., 2020).

The PDR can be an objective measure of nociception. It is an automatic response of cortical origin to stimuli, which we could use as an indicator of sensitivity to stimuli of minimal intensity. It will help us foresee the need for PreA before painful interventions. The PDR has been studied as a tool for objective monitoring of the analgesia-nociception balance (Abad-Torrent et al., 2017; Connelly et al., 2014; Duceau et al., 2017; Guglielminotti et al., 2015; Sabourdin et al., 2017; Wildemeersch et al., 2018). Studies propose PDR points to assess the need for analgesia in daily interventions, with optimal theoretical diagnostic yields performed patients with deep sedation (Paulus et al., 2013; Sabourdin., 2018). Vincclair et al. (2019) publishes that the pupillary dilation response measured through the PPI could be an adequate indicator of nociception in sedated critically ill patients with or without brain injury. Recently, Favre et al. (2024). identified a PDR>12% as the cut-off point for predicting nociception, with a sensitivity of 65%, a specificity of 94% and an AUC of 0.828 (95% CI 0.779-0.877) (25)-

Pupillometry could be a promising tool to provide adequate PreA before procedures in patients with mild levels of sedation. This indicator could be particularly beneficial for patients who cannot communicate pain, whose pain scores may be affected by their clinical status or sedation level, or as a predictor of pain before potentially painful procedures. Until now, no known stimuli of tolerable intensity and PDR were suitable for this type of patient. In this study, we used a PDR value after 20 mA with an accuracy close to 80% and positive likelihood ratios (LR+) of 4.1 (95% CI, 2.2-7.9) obtained in a previous project (López de Audícana-Jimenez de Aberasturi., 2023a, 2023b).

The PDR study that indicates nociception before interventions is booming. To the best of our knowledge, no studies have evaluated the clinical effectiveness of pupillometry in identifying the need for PreA.

Pupillometry identified patients with insufficient analgesia, and these patients had a lower incidence of pain. Compared with SCP, pupillometric monitoring detected 20% more patients likely to require PreA.

This study has observed a reduction in the risk of presenting pain associated with ETA diagnosed by BPS, ESCID and PDR in the pupillometric-guided group. The results were promising; nevertheless, we tried to identify possible factors that could have influenced the results. Some studies analyzed the responses to pain according to scales about APACHE II, level of sedation, and age (Ayasrah, 2019; Favre et al., 2024; Ito et al., 2022). We also found studies that postulated the presence of opioid treatment in a reduction of the pupillary response (Aissou et al., 2012; Barvais et al., 2003). On the other hand, we had previously studied the possible impact of these variables on BPS and PDR, observing that these factors did not affect the relationship between BPS and PDR (López de Audícana-Jimenez de Aberasturi et al., 2023b).

Based on analyzes we can confirm that the protective effect of PDR monitoring was observed regardless of sex, severity, level of sedation, and patient's baseline opioid sedoanalgesic treatment. We also analyzed the possibility that more PreA had been used in the group guided by pupillometry. Still, again, the multivariate analysis showed the protective effect of pupillometry on the development of pain.

Finally, this work was conducted following the methodological guidelines of randomized clinical trials. The data collected through pupillometry and the scores recorded on the behavioural scale were masked. However, the maintenance of double-blinding may have been affected because the protocol for the pupillometry-monitored patients was slightly different from that of the other patients.

It has been identified that some data is missing or unknown. This data loss is believed to have occurred randomly among the patients. However, to avoid any issues arising from not reaching the required sample size, 10% more patients were initially included in the study. As a result, it is likely that the impact of this situation on the accuracy and validity of the results has been minimized.

Pupillometry could facilitate and optimize therapeutic decision-making about PreA management. The results would be clinically relevant for incorporating this parameter into clinical practice. However, further studies with different daily interventions are needed to establish the validity of the indicator for monitoring the PreA before potentially painful care in critically ill patients.

Conclusion

The use of pupillometry to detect nociception and guide the PreA before ETA has a protective effect on pain diagnosed with the BPS, ESCID, and PDR scales, regardless of sex, severity level, sedation level and baseline opioid.

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Fig. 1 Intervention protocol

2.2.

5.2. ETA: endotracheal suctioning; IC: Informed consent; M: measurement; PDR: pupillary dilation reflex

Fig. 2 Flowchart

Table 1 General characteristics of the patients (n=92)

		Control group n=51	Intervention group n=41
Sex ratio	Male n(%)	33 (64.7)	33 (80.5)
	Female n(%)	18 (35.3)	8 (19.5)
Age (year), mean (SD)		63.2 (14.1)	66.0 (13.1)
	Unknown n=1		
Body mass index (kg/m2), mean (SD)		25.6 (4.09)	26.7 (4.51)
	Unknown n=4		
APACHE II		16.0 (7.40)	17.1 (8.41)
	Unknown n=4		
Glasgow		13.4 (3.02)	13.8 (3.15)
	Unknown n=2		
Bispectral index BIS , mean (SD)		57.6 (17.2)	63.2 (11.9)
	Unknown n=12		
RASS , mean (SD)		-3.13 (1.07)	-2.91 (0.91)
	Unknown n=2		
Admission	Acute respiratory failure n(%)	7 (13.7%)	7 (17.1%)
	Sepsis n(%)	5 (9.8%)	5 (12.2%)
	Postoperative n(%)	22 (43.1%)	22 (53.7%)
	Choronarian n(%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (4.9%)
	Multiple trauma n(%)	7 (13.7%)	2 (4.9%)
	Neurocritical n(%)	7 (13.7%)	2 (4.9%)
	Unknown n(%)	3 (5.9%)	1 (2.4%)
Sedative, analgesic and vasoactive drugs during the procedure	Midazolam n(%)	6 (11.8%)	6(14.6%)
	Propofol n(%)	35 (68.6%)	28 (68.3%)
	Midazolam and Propofol n(%)	3 (5.8%)	2 (4.88%)
	No Sedatives	7 (13.7%)	5 (12.2%)
	Fentanyl n(%)	17 (33.3%)	22 (53.7%)
	Remifentanyl n(%)	24 (47.1%)	15 (36.6%)
	Morphine n(%)	3 (5.88%)	3 (7.32%)
	Various analgesic n(%)	1 (1.96%)	0 (0.00%)
	Norepinephrine, n (%)	37 (72.5%)	23 (56.1%)
	Dobutamine, n (%)	1 (1.96%)	3 (7.32%)
	Norepinephrine and Dobutamine	3 (5.88%)	0 (0.00%)
	No Inotropic	10 (19.6%)	15 (36.6%)

Data are presented as number of patients (n) and percentage (%), mean and Standard Deviation(SD), APACHE II: Acute Physiology And Chronic Health Evaluation; RASS: Richmond Agitation Sedation Scale; BIS: Bispectral index

Table 2 Main outcome in different group

Variable, n (%)		Control group	Intervention group	p-value
		n=51	n=41	
ANALGESIA	No	39 (76.5%)	23 (56.1%)	0.030
	Yes	10 (19.6%)	18 (43.9%)	
	Unknown	2 (3.9%)	0 (0.0%)	
PDR	No	21 (41.2%)	25 (61.0%)	0.059
	Yes	30 (58.8%)	16 (39.0%)	
BPS	No	21 (41.2%)	22 (53.7%)	0.326
	Yes	30 (58.8%)	19 (46.3%)	
ESCID	No	17 (33.3%)	18 (43.9%)	0.217
	Yes	31 (60.8%)	17 (41.5%)	
	Unknown	3 (5.9%)	6 (14.6%)	

Data are presented as number of patients (n) and percentage (%), Pupillary dilation reflex (PDR), Behavioral Pain Scale (BPS); Scale of Behavior Indicators of Pain (ESCID); Pain scores: BPS \geq 4, ESCID \geq 1, PDR \geq 11,5%

Table 3 Univariate and Multivariate analysis adjusted by sex, APACHE II, Remifentanil, BIS and Analgesia before ETA

	ESCID			BPS			PDR		
	OR	IC	p-value	OR	IC	p-value	OR	IC	p-value
Unadjusted	0.52	0.21- 1.26	0.147	0.61	0.26;1.39	0.234	0.45	0.19-1.04	0.061
Adjusted	0.29	0.09-0.88	0.030	0.34	0.12- 0.99	0.048	0.27	0.08-0.86	0.027

Data are presented as Odds Ratio (OR), confidence interval (CI), Pupillary dilation reflex (PDR), Behavioral Pain Scale (BPS); Scale of Behavior Indicators of Pain (ESCID)

Hosmer-Lemeshow test ESCID: $\chi^2=3.615$; p=0.823

Hosmer-Lemeshow test BPS: $\chi^2=3.162$; p=0.870

Hosmer-Lemeshow test PDR: $\chi^2=3.369$; p=0.84